

ДОСВІД ВИКОРИСТАННЯ СИМУЛЯЦІЙНИХ ФАНТОМНИХ КЛАСІВ НА ДОДИПЛОМНОМУ ЕТАПІ ОСВІТИ СТУДЕНТІВ СТОМАТОЛОГІЧНОГО ФАКУЛЬТЕТУ**Годованець О.І.***доктор медичних наук, професор
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Chief of the department***0000-0002-1889-3893****Rozhko V.***PhD, Ass. Professor***0000-0002-0757-9671***Department of pediatric dentistry
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В статті представлений досвід використання фантомних класів на додипломному етапі освіти студентів-стоматологів на кафедрі стоматології дитячого віку. Симуляційний фантом є інструментом навчання та вдосконалення практичних навичок застосування сучасних технологій для лікарів-стоматологів, що дозволяє надавати кваліфіковану та професійну стоматологічну допомогу в майбутньому. Організація занять у симуляційних класах, на додаток до традиційних занять на стоматологічних факультетах, разом із виробничою практикою, є сучасним і ефективним методом підвищення якості практичних навичок у майбутніх лікарів-стоматологів. Впровадження в навчальний процес підготовки медичних кадрів на всіх етапах медичної освіти з використанням симуляційних класів призведе до зниження лікарських помилок, зменшення ускладнень та підвищить якість виконання діагностичних маніпуляцій та надання медичної допомоги.

Abstract

This article presents experience of using phantom classes for undergraduate education of dentists at the department of pediatric dentistry. Simulation phantom are a tool for learning and improving skills of practical application of modern technologies for dentists, which allows providing qualified and professional dental care in the future. Organization of classes in simulation classes, in addition to traditional ones at dental faculty, together with practice, is a modern and effective method of improving the quality of practical skills of future dentists. Introduction to the educational process, on all stages of medical education, the using simulation classes will lead to reduce medical errors, reduce complications and increase the quality of diagnostic manipulations and medical care.

Ключові слова: медична освіта, стоматолог, студент, навчання, фантоми, симулятори.

Keywords: medical education, dentist, student, training, phantoms, simulators.

Introduction. Implementation of priority national projects in the field of health care, the reformation and modernization processes in the health care system have revealed the problem of professional training of medical workers with particular urgency. There is an acute shortage of highly qualified specialists. Therefore, it is natural that one of the main directions in the field of higher medical education is significantly strengthen the practical aspect of training future doctors while maintaining the appropriate level of theoretical knowledge.

Due to the rapid development of dentistry in our country and in worldwide, due to the emergence of new technologies, materials, techniques and types of treatment that should have a dentist, providing professional

dental care, there is a question of professional development and improving doctor's skills. Continuing professional development includes itself a set of measures aimed at improving the theoretical and practical skills of a dentist [1-3]. One of the types of improvement and development of doctor skills, is taking practical courses, classes on special simulations phantoms. Simulation phantoms are a tool for learning and improving skills of practical application of modern technologies for dentists, which allows providing qualified and professional dental care in future.

Simulation technologies in undergraduate education of dentists play special role, gives the opportunity for understanding of treatment protocols by modern

methods, learn and improve the necessary skills and their further full development in clinical practice [4-5]. One of the ways to solve this problem is to create phantom classes at the dental faculties of universities.

Main part. Modern dental education require from high school teacher not only theoretical knowledge, but also sufficient experience in providing dental care. This should encourage the teacher to continuous professional growth. In the dental field, there are new methods of diagnosis and treatment which are extremely fast developing and should be reported to future specialists, encourage them to cooperate and motivate to self-mastery of modern techniques. It known that integral part of the educational process is the systematization of theoretical material, analysis and practical experience. However, to improve the educational process, its modernization, it is currently advisable to introduce classes of simulation technologies for dental students 4-5 courses.

The use of modern simulators allows the student to compliance with professional instructions of the teacher during the work repeatedly, to automatically perform a certain action and in this way gain practical experience and skills without compromising the patient's health. At the same time, keep in mind that the simulation is not a simple multiple mechanical training of actions, and this should be a conscious formation practical skills based on quality theoretical training of

student. In the conditions of simulation training the activity of students is directed not only for mastering certain skills, but also for teamwork and skills communicate with the patient. For many students, this can be overcome professional fear, seeing the patient in a critical situation, for others - allows to form in them leadership and organizational qualities.

In the phantom training class, dental facilities are equipped for everyone necessary modules for tooth preparation, phantom imitations of the head and jaws with replaceable teeth. Changing the position of the head is important for the work of skills of interaction of doctors with the assistant, when working on the principle of "four hands", in compliance with ergonomic requirements. The maximum imitation of real dental reception has created [6-8].

Organization of classes in simulation classes, in addition to traditional ones in dental departments, together with practice, is a modern and effective method of improving the quality of practical skills of future dentists, as evidenced by the experience of the implemented phantom classes at the department of pediatric dentistry of Bukovinian State Medical University (Fig. 1-3). There are simulators - dental phantoms of the head on a tripod, which completely simulate the patient (head with an anatomical rubber mask and models of jaws with the possibility of replacing teeth and different body positions in the dental chair).

Fig.1-2. Practical lesson in phantom class.

For example, the following practical skills we can perform on phantoms:

preparation of cavities of I-V classes according to Black's classification; application of rubber dam, sealing of carious cavities of all classes with different sealing materials; tooth restoration; endodontic treatment and filling of root canals, implementation of clinical

stages of manufacturing various orthopedic and orthodontic appliance in pediatric dentistry, installation of braces, installation of retainers, work with an assistant in four hands. It should be noted that for high-quality simulation training the department uses not only phantoms, but also modern dental instruments, equipment and materials.

Fig. 3. Orthodontics. Installation of braces.

The use of such technologies in the educational process increases student interest and is an important part of improving skills of future specialists. This allows to increase digestibility educational material, the quality and effectiveness of the educational process, contributes formation of students' motivation to study.

Thus, a graduate with theoretical knowledge, possessing practical skills and working on a virtual algorithm for practical manipulations in the phantom class in conditions close to the real situation, by repeatedly repeating skills and analyzing mistakes achieves perfection of their professional abilities.

The use of simulation learning technology makes it possible to consolidate obtained theoretical

knowledge, master practical skills without risk for the patient, to objectively assess the achieved level of skill, to reduce the level of psychological stress during the first manipulations; to approach imitation of activity to reality with a high degree of reliability; hone the clarity, correctness and speed of action that can save the patient's life; analyze and correct mistakes [6-8].

Thus, conducting phantom classes for students allows to study protocols with algorithms for the diagnostic and treatment of simulated situations of personal actions and team interaction in the choice of treatment tactics in different clinical situations and correct most medical errors.

Introduction to the educational process, on all stages of medical education, the using simulation classes will lead to reduce medical errors, reduce complications and increase the quality of diagnostic manipulations and medical care.

Conclusions. 1. Use of simulation technologies in preparation future doctors significantly improves both the theoretical level of knowledge and mastering professional and individual competencies, which improves quality training students.

2. It is worth noting that simulation training and skills development on phantoms and models does not replace, but only complements the preparation for the real practical work, and provides control of the teacher over the quality of performance each student action and reduce the time to prepare them.

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МІКРОБІОЛОГІЧНА ХАРАКТЕРИСТИКА ХВОРИХ НА ГЕНЕРАЛІЗОВАНИЙ КАТАРАЛЬНИЙ ГІНГІВІТ

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MICROBIOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF PATIENTS WITH GENERALIZED CATARRHAL GINGIVITIS

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Анотація

У статті наведені отримані результати дослідження мікрофлори порожнини рота 82 хворих на генералізований катаральний гінгівіт з хронічним та загостреним перебігом до проведення лікувально-профілактичних заходів. Для ідентифікації основних пародонтопатогенів застосовували полімеразну ланцюгову реакцію з використанням ДНК-зондів із зворотної ДНК-гібридизації. Біохімічну ідентифікацію анаеробних бактерій, стрептококів і грамнегативних бактерій проводили за допомогою тест-системи фірми API (Франція).